

Design and Manufacture of Non-Contact Moving Load for Experimental Analysis of Beams

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Abstract : Dynamic tests are an important step of the design of engineering structures, because the accuracy of predictions of theoretical-numerical procedures can be assessed. In experimental test of moving loads that is one of the major research topics, the load is modeled as a simple moving mass or a small vehicle. This paper deals with the applicability of Non-Contact Moving Load (NML) for vibration analysis. For this purpose, an experimental set-up is designed to generate the different types of NML including constant and harmonic. The proposed method relies on pressurized air which is useful, especially when dealing with fragile or sensitive structures. To demonstrate the performance of this system, the set-up is employed for a modal analysis of a beam and detecting crack of the beam. The obtained results indicate that the experimental set-up for NML can be an attractive alternative to the moving load problems.

Keywords : experimental analysis, moving load, non-contact excitation, materials engineering

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